

Dyes Derived from Acenaphthenequinone. Part III. Azines and Indigoid Vat Dyes.

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This communication, which is an extension of the work of Sircar and Guha (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 335) and Guha (*ibid.*, 1931, 582), embodies the preparation of acenaphthaphenazines containing

the chromophoric group, $-N \begin{array}{l} \diagup O \\ \diagdown \end{array}$ in the "b₃z₀"-ring of the mole-

cule and a study of their properties. The azines obtained are 9-nitro-, 3-chloro-9-nitro-, 3-bromo-9-nitro-, and 3:4:9-trinitroacenaphthaphenazines. All these coloured bodies are characterised by their very sparing solubility in alcohol. Although very stable they volatilise without decomposition when heated strongly above their melting points yielding coloured vapours of the respective substances which deposit again as pure dyes. The first three compounds dye wool a shade of lemon-yellow and the last named produces a deep yellow shade from an acid bath when freshly precipitated by water from strong sulphuric acid solution.

9-Aminoacenaphthaphenazine has also been obtained from the corresponding nitro compound by reduction (*cf.* Heckendorn, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929, **12**, 50). The identity of the compound was established by the preparation of the same aminoazine from acenaphthenequinone and reduced chrysoidine (*cf.* Witt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1886, **49**, 401). It dyes wool in bright yellow shades from an acid bath which is fast to alkali and acid but not to light.

The following table shows that the dyeing shades of some of the azines mentioned are in no way inferior to those of the corresponding phenanthraquinone derivatives (Heim, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 2305; Witt, *loc. cit.*).

Compound.	Dyeing shade on wool.
9-Nitroacenaphthaphenazine	Lemon yellow
Nitrophenanthraphenazine	" "
9-Aminoacenaphthaphenazine.	Bright "
Aminophenanthraphenazine	" "

Finally, three derivatives of 2-thionaphtheneacenaphthylene-indigo, commercially known as Ciba scarlet G (Rezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908 **29**, 306; Grob, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 3331; E. P. 34408; A. P. 891690 containing Cl, Br and NO₂ respectively in the

acenaⁿphthene part of the molecule, have been prepared*. These substances bear resemblance to azines exhibiting their distinctive sulphuric acid reaction. Further, they behave similarly to nitroazines (*loc. cit.*), when heated above their melting points. Alkaline hydrosulphite forms a coloured vat with each of these compounds from which the dye can be reprecipitated by treatment with air. The dyed shades are quite even and fast. These dyes were also found quite suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath when freshly precipitated unchanged from strong sulphuric acid solution by water.

A comparison of the scarlet red shade obtained from the chloro- and bromoindigoid derivatives on cotton as well as on wool with that of the same shade of Ciba scarlet G (prepared for the purpose) on same medium, exhibits that notwithstanding the decisive redder shades of the former two compounds, brilliancy and glazy pleasantness are prominent in the shade of the latter, the mother compound. Work in this line is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

9-Nitroacenaphthaphenazine.

The crystalline yellow precipitate, produced by bringing together acenaⁿphthenequinone (0.72 g.) and 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.61 g.) in 50 c. c. of boiling glacial acetic acid, after being purified by boiling successively with a small quantity of alcohol and acetic acid in which the condensation product was only sparingly solution separated from pyridine in beautiful lemon-yellow prisms or from aniline in thin square plates, m.p. above 810°. It is soluble in aniline or pyridine, sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene, or amyl alcohol and insoluble in caustic alkalis, ammonia or ether. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a reddish brown colour and when reprecipitated by water dyes wool in lemon-yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 18.99. $C_{18}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.04 per cent.).

* In German patent 282170 halogenated derivatives of Ciba scarlet G, obtained by condensing thioindoxyl with halogen derivatives of acenaⁿphthenequinone have been described. Editor.

3-Chloro-9-nitroacenaphthaphenazine separated in lemon-yellow clusters of needles during heating 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.43 g.) and 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.31 g.) in 40 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid for 15 minutes. It was first boiled with alcohol and then for sometime with a little acetic acid. The residue recrystallised from acetic in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 287° (shrinking previously at 284°). It is soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetic acid, pyridine or amyl alcohol, sparingly soluble in alcohol or acetone. The substance gives a deep reddish brown solution with concentrated sulphuric acid and dyes wool in lemon-yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: Cl, 10.26. $C_{18}H_8O_2N_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.64 per cent.).

3-Bromo-9-nitroacenaphthaphenazine was similarly obtained in rectangular crystalline precipitate from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.52 g.) and the diamine (0.31 g.) in 53 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and crystallised from pyridine in fine lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 295°. It is similar in appearance and in solubility to the preceding compound and dyes wool in lemon-yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: Br, 21.39. $C_{18}H_8O_2N_3Br$ requires Br, 21.16 per cent.).

3:4:9-Trinitroacenaphthaphenazine.—A solution of 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.31 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid (16 c.c.) was added to the solution of powdered 3:4-dinitroacenaphthenequinone (0.54 g.) in 70 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and the mixture kept boiling for 20 minutes. The resulting yellowish brown liquid when cooled, separated the condensation product in deep yellow rectangular plates which after being purified by boiling with alcohol recrystallised from moderately strong acetic acid. The azine melts at 300-1°, and gives a light yellow solution in concentrated sulphuric acid and dyes wool in deep yellow shades from an acid bath. It is soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetone, acetic acid, pyridine or aniline, sparingly soluble in alcohol, ligroin or amyl alcohol. (Found: N, 18.12. $C_{18}H_7O_6N_5$ requires N, 17.99 per cent.).

9-Aminoacenaphthaphenazine.—(i) 9-Nitroacenaphthaphenazine (1 g.) suspended in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.) was reduced by stannous chloride (4 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.). The mixture was boiled on the water-bath with occasional shaking. It first turned pink-red and then to dark magenta-red and finally violet coloured precipitate of the hydrochloride of the base separated in 1½–1¾ hours. Water (180 c.c.) was added to the reaction mixture and the whole warmed, filtered, and the alcohol distilled off. The

dark magenta-red solution on treatment with strong ammonia slowly separated the aminoazine in deep yellow flakes. This was collected and further purified by dissolving in a little cold dilute hydrochloric acid (2*N* approx.) and excess of cold water and liberating the base again by the addition of ammonia. It was finally crystallised from xylene or in better yield from aniline in silky rectangular prisms. The crystals were thoroughly washed with cold dilute acetic acid (2*N* approx.) and boiling water. It does not melt below 310°. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with an orange-red coloration and it dyes wool in bright yellow shades from an acid bath. It is readily soluble in chloroform, acetone, alcohol, amyl alcohol, pyridine or aniline, moderately soluble in benzene or ether. It dissolves in cold glacial acetic acid yielding reddish brown solution from which the base can be reprecipitated by the addition of alkalis. It is insoluble in cold dilute acetic acid. (Found: N, 15·64. $C_{18}H_{11}N_3$ requires N, 15·61 per cent.).

(ii) *Second method*.—Powdered chrysoidine hydrochloride (1·8 g.), dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (55 c.c.) was reduced by gradually adding zinc dust (9—10 g.). The colourless filtered solution was added to the solution of acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) in 55 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and the mixture boiled for 2—3 minutes. On adding powdered anhydrous sodium carbonate to the cooled deep brown solution and stirring, a pasty mass was obtained. This was treated with water (250 c.c.) and the separated brown amorphous precipitate filtered, and washed with hot water. It was purified in the same way as in the first method and found to be identical with the preceding aminoazine. (Found: N, 15·39. $C_{18}H_{11}N_3$ requires N, 15·61 per cent.).

2-Thionaphthene-8' (3'-chloro) acenaphthylene-indigo.

3 Chloroacenaphthenequinone (0·64 g.) in boiling glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 c.c.) and to this mixture a solution of 3-hydroxythionaphthene (0·45 g.) in 25 c.c. of hot glacial acetic acid added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath at 80-85° for 10 minutes when deep scarlet

red needle shaped crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with acetic acid and hot water. For further purification it was successively boiled with a little alcohol and acetic acid and finally crystallised from acetic acid, pyridine or amyl alcohol in scarlet red needles, m. p. 280°. It is soluble in benzene, chloroform, xylene, pyridine, aniline, amyl alcohol or acetic acid and sparingly soluble in acetone, alcohol or ligroin. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it with a deep green solution from which water reprecipitates the original substance which dyes wool from an acid bath in scarlet red shade. With alkaline hydrosulphite it gives a bluish violet vat by which cotton is coloured scarlet red when exposed to atmospheric oxygen. (Found: Cl, 10.54. $C_{20}H_9O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 10.18 per cent.).

2-Thionaphthene-8''(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene-indigo was prepared from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.52 g.) and 3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.3 g.) in the same way as and possesses properties similar to the preceding compound, m. p. 287°. (Found: Br, 20.21. $C_{20}H_9O_2BrS$ requires Br, 20.35 per cent.).

2-Thionaphthene-8''(3':4'-dinitro)-acenaphthylene-indigo. — The solutions of 3:4-dinitroacenaphthenequinone (0.27 g.) in 50 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.15 g.) in 30 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were made free from dissolved air by passing dry carbon dioxide for 5 minutes and mixed together and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid added. The mixture was boiled for 5-6 minutes by which time dark red crystalline precipitate separated. This was filtered at once, washed first with acetic acid and then with hot water. After being boiled with alcohol it was crystallised from pyridine in hexagonal prisms, not melting below 300°. It is soluble in pyridine or xylene, moderately soluble in chloroform or benzene and sparingly soluble in alcohol, amyl alcohol, or acetic acid. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid giving a blackish brown solution and dyes wool in dark red shades from an acid bath. The vat formed by the action of the alkaline hydrosulphite on this dye is yellow-brown and on exposure to air the dark red colouring matter is regenerated on cotton fibre. (Found: N, 6.75. $C_{20}H_8O_6N_2S$ requires N, 6.93 per cent.).

I avail myself of this opportunity to express my thanks to Dr. K.S. Caldwell, Principal, Science College, for his interest during the progress of the work.

